

1 ***Regulating The Electronic Configuration of Low-Dimensional Hybrid Perovskites via Organic***
2 ***Cations for Self-Powered Ultraviolet Photodetectors***

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15
16 **Abstract**

17 Ultraviolet photodetectors (UPDs) based on low-dimensional halide perovskites have
18 undergone rapid development. Here, regulation of the electronic configuration of low-dimensional
19 hybrid perovskites are reported via organic cations for self-powered UPDs. For the first time, it is
20 determine that the rational design of organic cation phenyl alkylammonium can effectively prevent
21 phonon scattering thus increasing charge carrier extraction in low dimensional lead chlorine
22 perovskite thin-films. As a result, the exciton-binding energy can be reduced to 62.91 meV in
23 (PMA)₂PbCl₄ perovskite films with a charge-carrier mobility of 0.335 cm² V⁻¹ s⁻¹. The fabricated
24 (PMA)₂PbCl₄-based self-powered UPDs has achieved a high detectivity of 6.32 × 10¹³ jones with
25 a low noise current of 0.35 pA Hz^{-1/2} under zero bias. A further demonstration of images with high
26 UV to visible light rejection ratio under weak-light illumination of 70 nW cm⁻² highlights the
27 feasible potential application of low-dimensional perovskite..

28 **Keywords:** UV photodetector, low-dimensional perovskite, self-powered model, quantum well,
29 charge carrier transport

31 INTRODUCTION

32 Ultraviolet photodetectors (UPDs) with high anti-interference ability are widely used in diverse
33 applications, including optical communication and environmental monitoring, etc.^[1] Recently, the
34 self-powered UPDs have shown their value for easy-to-fabricate devices for Internet of Things
35 (IoT) technology compatibility. Though III-V group and II-VI compound-based semiconductors
36 are currently dominating the UPD market. However, manufacturing these devices requires a
37 capital-intensive fabrication infrastructure. For a sustainable IoT ecosystem, facile and low-cost
38 photoactive materials are desirable to develop photodetectors that can operate in self-powered
39 mode.^{[1][5],[6]} Three-dimensional (3D) perovskite semiconductors have shown their promise in
40 photoelectric-converting devices benefitting from their special lattice characteristics, remarkable
41 optoelectronic properties, and facile low-temperature fabrication methods.^[7] In this context, lead
42 halide perovskites have received considerable attention for photodetectors which principally
43 require an ultra-fast response, high sensitivity, and ultralow detection limit.^[1] Reducing the
44 dimensionality of lead halide perovskite semiconductors could further strengthen their ability of
45 high signal-to-noise ratio ^{[14][15]}. Especially, the low-dimensional perovskite-based semiconductors
46 with wide band gaps possess intrinsic optional sensitivity to UV radiation and robustness against
47 harsh conditions. Moreover, low-dimensional perovskite also prevails as a valuable opportunity to
48 build platforms for chemical refinement to meet real-world operational needs.^{[16],[17]} However, due
49 to a weakening of dielectric screening, the materials with low-dimensional structures are
50 recognized to exhibit a perfected quasi-particle correction and excitonic effect.^[18] The strong
51 quantum confinement in low-dimensional perovskites not only induces exciton-exciton
52 annihilation but also imposes Auger recombination. Meanwhile, the low-dimensional perovskites
53 generally exhibit an anisotropy of charge transport which appears strongly in the direction parallel
54 to the inorganic photoactive layers and is expected as the insulating character of organic cations.^[19]
55 Tuning the thickness or the type of metal halide layers and modulating the organic cation layer are
56 effective methods to regulate the quantum confinement effect.^{[20][21]} Arguably, tuning the electrical
57 potential across the barrier and the “well” layer provides an opportunity to optimize the
58 optoelectronic abilities of low-dimensional metal halide perovskites.

59 Here, we report the control of quantum confinement in low-dimensional lead chorine hybrid
60 perovskites benefits from the large bandgap for ultraviolet photodetectors. Phenyl alkylammonium

61 cations with four different alkyl chains (*i.e.*, benzylamine (PMA), 2-phenethylamine (PEA), 3-
62 phenyl-1-propylamine (PPA) and 4-phenyl-1-butylamine (PBA)) were selected as organic
63 components in low-dimensional perovskites to regulate confinement potential and barrier length.
64 The resultant compounds with shorter phenyl alkylammonium cations (*i.e.*, PMA and PEA)
65 possess two-dimensional (2D) characteristics. Other two compounds with longer phenyl
66 alkylammonium cations (*i.e.*, PPA and PBA) form a one-dimensional (1D) electronic structure.
67 Intending to achieve the self-powered UPDs with effective exciton dissociation and carrier
68 transport, we focused on the impact of quantum well (QW) structure and barrier potential of low-
69 dimensional perovskite absorbers on their photoelectric conversion capability. Our detailed study
70 reveals that the organic cations regulation significantly impacts the charge transport properties for
71 both 2D and 1D electronic structured perovskites. This stems from the reduced exciton-binding
72 energy and improved carrier mobility. Consequently, the fabricated UPDs using PMA cation-
73 based 2D perovskite as the photo-sensitive layer with thinner barrier length and small electron
74 diffusion barrier potential demonstrate a notable performance of a large responsivity (0.247 A W^{-1}),
75 a low noise equivalent power (NEP, $0.35 \text{ pA Hz}^{-1/2}$) and a high detectivity ($6.32 \times 10^{13} \text{ jones}$).
76 We put forward the importance of quantum well designing for effective carrier extraction in low-
77 dimensional perovskite optoelectronic devices.

78 **Results**

79 The low-dimensional hybrid perovskites consist of a single-terminated inorganic moiety sheet
80 separated by a bilayer of alkylammonium cations. These units interconnect through van *der* Waals
81 interaction among the alkyl chains, thus forming a QW structure.^{[20][22]} We examined the impact
82 of quantum confinement in low dimensional perovskites with four functional alkyl amine
83 derivatives differentiating only in the alkyl chain between their common benzene ring and the
84 terminal amine, *i.e.*, PMA, PEA, PPA, and PBA (Figure S1). Thus, the change of organic ligands
85 can modulate band structure from 3D to 2D and effectively to 1D models featuring confinement
86 effect by the formation of corner-sharing and/or face-sharing octahedrons. The structural skeleton
87 (Figure 1, a-d), illustrates the (PMA)₂PbCl₄ and (PEA)₂PbCl₄ perovskites are constructed with a
88 2D structure consisting of a formula of A₂PbCl₄ (A=PMA or PEA) with PbCl₄²⁻ octahedra units
89 acting as corner-sharing, while the PPA- and PBA-based perovskites lead to 1D structure with
90 Pb₂Cl₇³⁻ units showing face-sharing characteristic.^{[23][24]} The crystal structure of 2D (PMA)₂PbCl₄

91 and $(\text{PEA})_2\text{PbCl}_4$ is monoclinic with space group $\text{Cmc}2_1$. The unit cell of 1D $(\text{PPA})_3\text{Pb}_2\text{Cl}_7$ and
 92 $(\text{PBA})_3\text{Pb}_2\text{Cl}_7$ is orthorhombic with the structure adopting the noncentro-symmetric polar $\text{Pca}2_1$
 93 space group.

94
 95 Fig. 1. Structure and optical characteristics in perovskite films. (a-d) Crystal structure of two-
 96 dimensional perovskite $(\text{PMA})_2\text{PbCl}_4$ and $(\text{PEA})_2\text{PbCl}_4$, one-dimensional perovskite
 97 $(\text{PPA})_3\text{Pb}_2\text{Cl}_7$ and $(\text{PBA})_3\text{Pb}_2\text{Cl}_7$; (e-h) the GIWAXS patterns for the PEA-, PMA-, PPA- and
 98 PBA- low dimensional films; (i, j) the corresponding pole figures; (k) UV-vis absorption
 99 spectroscopy (solid line) and the corresponding PL spectra (dotted line) of the four different
 100 perovskite samples. $E_x=325 \text{ nm}$.

101 We employed the spin-coating method to deposit phase-pure homogeneity and achieved full
 102 coverage in thin films. The film morphologies (Fig. S2) were unraveled by scanning electron
 103 microscopy, suggesting uniform and dense films. The characterization of thin films is
 104 complemented by Grazing incident wide-angle X-ray scattering (GIWAXS) measurements. The
 105 formation of 2D and 1D structures is suggested by indexing the Bragg peaks observed in GIWAXS
 106 and the corresponding intensity versus the scattering vector q (where $q=4\pi\sin(\theta)/\lambda$ for the

107 diffraction features at azimuth 90°). The strong scattering peak (Figure 1e) at $q=3.7 \text{ nm}^{-1}$ is
108 corresponding to the (200) plane and that at $q=7.4 \text{ nm}^{-1}$ is consistent with the (400) plane of the
109 perovskite ((PMA)₂PbCl₄). The preference for a single $n=1$ orientation indicates a reduced
110 distribution of quantum well widths.^[25] Analogous features were also observed for the other three
111 samples (Figure 1, f-h). This manifests a high crystalline orientation along the (h00) planes in thin
112 films, *i.e.*, with the inorganic octahedra perpendicular to the substrate surface. The QW orientation
113 for the glass/SnO₂ substrate was investigated intimately with the pole figure of the Azimuth angle
114 of the (200) plane (Figures 1, i and j). The single sharp peak at the 90° pole angle indicates that
115 the QWs are extremely oriented. The formation of an inorganic layer perpendicular to the substrate
116 constructs channels for vertical charge transport, presumably benefitting vertical device
117 architecture. The vertical orientation preference can also be embodied by conductivity anisotropy
118 along the direction for in-plane and out-of-plane as a consequence of the conductive nature of
119 inorganic layers and the insulating feature of bulky organic cations.^[26] We also fabricated devices
120 of sandwich structure and gap-type structure with the low-dimensional lead chlorine perovskite
121 films (Fig. S3a) to estimate the conductivity along the in-plane ($\sigma_{\text{in-plane}}$) and out-of-plane ($\sigma_{\text{out-plane}}$)
122 *via* the space charge limited current method. The conductivities were extracted (Fig. S3b-e) and
123 tabulated in Table S1. We noted that the ratio of $\sigma_{\text{out-plane}}/\sigma_{\text{in-plane}}$ for the PMA- (7.13×10^4) and PEA-
124 (3.47×10^4) based 2D lead chlorine perovskites is larger than that of PPA- (1.06×10^4) and PBA-
125 (0.29×10^4) based samples, ascribing to the preferred out-of-plane orientation for the formers.

126 The absorption characterization (solid lines) and steady-state photoluminescence (PL) spectra
127 (dashed lines) of four different samples were measured (Figure 1k). The narrow and intense
128 exciton absorption observed in the violet region stems from the electronic transition in the
129 inorganic layer.^[27] A substantial and sharp exciton band edge emission signal in a short wavelength
130 region ($\sim 350 \text{ nm}$) was also observed in PL studies. The exciton emission for thin films shifted to
131 higher energy when the cations altered from PEA to PMA, and from PBA to PPA. The four phenyl
132 alkylammonium cations have the sole difference in $(-\text{CH}_2-)_m$ units (*i.e.*, $m=1$ for PMA, $m=2$ for
133 PEA, $m=3$ for PBA, and $m=4$ for PPA in Fig. S1), which may result in a different thickness
134 between the inorganic frameworks thus turn the confinement effect.^[28] This possibly explains the
135 shift of exciton emission. In addition to fluorescent luminescence, the four perovskite films exhibit
136 separate, broad ‘white’ emissions in the long wavelength range. This is a typical characteristic of
137 the self-trapped exciton (STE).^[29] The charge carriers induced by a strong electron-phonon

138 coupling lead to the generation of STE.^[30] Compared to the 2D-(PMA)₂PbCl₄, a stronger STE in
 139 2D-(PEA)₂PbCl₄ can facilitate the charge carriers capture. Similarly, the 1D-(PBA)₃Pb₂Cl₇-based
 140 samples also possess higher carrier capture potential than 1D-(PPA)₃Pb₂Cl₇.

141 The carrier-phonon coupling effect is pertinent to both the motion and rotation of the inorganic
 142 lead halide cage as well as the deflection of organic cations. It is also connected to the force of the
 143 quantum confinement effect in the QW structure which impacts the charge carrier transport.^[30] To
 144 analyze the effectiveness of charge carrier-phonon coupling for solution-processed perovskite thin
 145 films, we performed temperature-dependent steady-state PL (TDPL) studies with an excitation at
 146 325 nm over a temperature range from 80 to 320 K at a sweeping rate of 20 K. The PL spectra
 147 (Fig. S4a-d) show the corresponding excitonic emissions.^{[32][33]} The localized potential fluctuations
 148 caused by the compositional and structural inhomogeneity in the QW structure of layered
 149 perovskite can spatially trap free carriers, thus perturbing carriers transportation.^[34] To determine
 150 the degree of localization effect (σ), we evaluated the temperature-dependent emission energy with
 151 the band-tail model from the following equation.

$$152 \quad E(T) = E_g - \frac{\alpha T^2}{T+\beta} + \frac{\sigma^2}{k_B T} \quad (1)$$

153 where $E(T)$ is the emission energy at T , E_g , k_B is the energy gap at 0 K and the Boltzmann constant,
 154 α and β are the Varshni coefficients.^{[35][36]} The value of σ was extracted from the plot of PL peak
 155 energy as a function of temperature (Fig. S4, e-h, the top) with Eq. 1 and the results are tabulated
 156 in Table 1. Subsequently, the relatively small value of σ observed for 2D-based perovskite (10.48
 157 and 24.83 meV) indicates a reduced localization effect for the 1D-based samples (41.52 and 71.72
 158 meV). A slightly weaker localization effect of PMA₂PbCl₄ than PEA₂PbCl₄ can be attributed to
 159 effective carrier transportation.

160 **Table 1.** The extracted values for the parameters of inhomogeneous broadening (Γ_0), charge carrier
 161 LO-phonon coupling strength (γ_0), exciton binding energy (E_b), and carrier location energies (σ).

Perovskites	σ (meV)	Γ_0 (meV)	γ_0 (meV)	E_b (meV)
(PMA) ₂ PbCl ₄	10.48	38.96	101.26	62.91
(PEA) ₂ PbCl ₄	24.83	36.54	162.10	73.74
(PPA) ₃ Pb ₂ Cl ₇	41.52	98.47	133.98	101.47

(PBA) ₃ Pb ₂ Cl ₇	71.72	231.29	245.39	105.24
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162 Phenyl alkylammonium-based low-dimensional perovskites exhibit strong inhomogeneous
163 broadening in PL spectra (Fig. S5).^[16] To quantify the mechanism of the electron–phonon coupling
164 in organic-inorganic hybrid semiconductors, we studied temperature-dependent emission
165 broadening.^[37] Electron-phonon coupling is very important to carrier recombination dynamics in
166 perovskites, which refers to the interaction between charge carriers and lattice vibrations (phonons).
167 By extracting the full width at half-maximum (FWHM) of the PL emission peaks $\Gamma(T)$, the
168 inhomogeneous broadening characteristic was evaluated to verify the property involved in the
169 Fröhlich coupling.^[38]

$$170 \quad \Gamma(T) = \Gamma_0 + \frac{\gamma_0}{\exp\left(\frac{E_{LO}}{k_B T}\right)} \quad (2)$$

171 where Γ_0 is a temperature-independent inhomogeneous broadening term arising from the scattering
172 due to disorder and impurities in perovskite materials.^[39] The Fröhlich coupling is proportional to
173 the occupation numbers of the longitudinal-optical (LO) phonons. The LO phonons were given by
174 the Bose–Einstein distribution function ($\gamma_0/\exp(E_{LO}/k_B T)$), where E_{LO} is an energy representative
175 of the frequency for the LO phonon mode and γ_0 represents the Fröhlich coupling strength.^[40] Fig.
176 S4 (e-h, the bottom) presents the Gauss-fitted FWHMs for TDPL, from which we can deduce the
177 quantum confinement effects strength in a QW structure. The extracted value of Γ_0 is 38.96 meV
178 and the strength of charge carrier LO-phonon coupling (γ_0) is 101.26 meV for PMA₂PbCl₄, which
179 is lower than the other three perovskites (Table 1). This suggests that the LO-phonon coupling is
180 considerably reduced for the PMA-based sample. For photodetector operation, a small γ_0 can
181 reduce the scattering during charge transport in perovskite film, thus increasing carrier mobility.
182 Subsequently, this would contribute to improved carrier injection and transport efficiency.

183 Due to a dielectric constant mismatch between organic spacer cations and the inorganic
184 framework in low dimensional perovskite, the excitons can be restrained by a strong Coulombic
185 force.^{[41][42]} In the evaluation of binding energies, the noticeable interference of STE emission can
186 be ignored taking into account that the STE emission at the low energy range of such compositions
187 is spectrally separated from band-edge excitonic emission. The integrated TDPL intensity $I(T)$ can
188 be explained.^[43]

189
$$I(T) = \frac{I_0}{1 + B e^{-E_{ex}/(k_B T)}} \quad (3)$$

190 where E_{ex} is the excitonic binding energy, I_0 is the integrated PL intensity at 0 K, and B is the
191 preexponential factor. By fitting the integrated PL intensity as a function of the reciprocal
192 temperature (Fig. S4, i-l), the exciton-binding energy E_{ex} for PMA₂PbCl₄, PEA₂PbCl₄,
193 (PPA)₃Pb₂Cl₇, and (PBA)₃Pb₂Cl₇ are estimated to be 62.91, 73.74, 101.47, 105.24 meV,
194 respectively (Table 1). The lower exciton-binding energy in PMA₂PbCl₄ indicates a weaker
195 confinement of free excitons in the QW structure free charges are generated predominantly. This
196 result follows the order of increase in the alkyl chain.

197 Femtosecond transient absorption spectroscopy (fs-TA) was performed to directly access the
198 exciton dissociation and free carrier generation processes in the low-dimensional absorbers.^[44] The
199 details are included in supporting information. Fig. S6 shows the TA spectra of the PMA₂PbCl₄,
200 PEA₂PbCl₄, (PPA)₃Pb₂Cl₇, and (PBA)₃Pb₂Cl₇ employing 300 nm excitation, respectively.
201 Together with the strong ground state bleaching (GSB) signals at 341 and 340 nm for the
202 PMA₂PbCl₄ and PEA₂PbCl₄ (336 and 337 nm for (PPA)₃Pb₂Cl₇, and (PBA)₃Pb₂Cl₇) perovskites,
203 a broad excited-state absorption extending into longer wavelength range was also observed. The
204 photoinduced absorption (PIA) signals at short range (below around 335 nm) and long wavelength
205 (beyond around 345 nm) can be associated with hot and free charge carriers. We also found the
206 intensity of broad PIA signal for PMA₂PbCl₄ ascribed to free carriers was 1.5 times higher than
207 PEA₂PbCl₄, demonstrating in the former there exists efficient exciton dissociation^[45] (Figure 2, a
208 and b). The broad PIA signals for 1D perovskites presented ignorable differences in their intensity
209 (Fig. S7, a, and b). The kinetic traces of GSB and PIA recovery of the four kinds of materials are
210 shown in Figure 2 (c and d) and Fig. S7 (c and d). Compared with PEA₂PbCl₄ (1542±16 ps), the
211 longer lifetime for GSB recovery in the PMA₂PbCl₄ perovskites (2502±33 ps) provides evidence
212 for slow electron/hole recombination, which is consistent with its low exciton-binding energy.
213 Furthermore, (PPA)₃Pb₂Cl₇ and (PBA)₃Pb₂Cl₇ samples indicate a difficult exciton dissociation as
214 a result of the fast decay of GSB.

215
 216 **Fig 2. Charge carrier dynamics.** Femtosecond transient absorption (fs-TA) spectra of the 2D
 217 (PMA)₂PbCl₄ (a) and (PEA)₂PbCl₄ (b) perovskites following 300 nm laser excitation at different
 218 time delays. Kinetic traces of the (PMA)₂PbCl₄ (c) and (PEA)₂PbCl₄ (d), monitored at the ground
 219 state bleaching (GSB) maxima and photoinduced absorption (PIA) signals, respectively.

220

221 The performance of perovskites-based devices was affected critically by carrier mobility. The
 222 reduced screening effect of charge impurities in low-dimensional perovskites leads to a large
 223 scattering cross-section and low carrier mobility.^[46] The larger dielectric constant organic layer
 224 compared with the inorganic layer can shield charged impurities, reducing the cross section for
 225 scattering. Here we assessed the temperature dependence of charge-carrier mobility (μ) in terms
 226 of $\mu \propto T^m$ where m describes the charge transport-phonon scattering relation.^[47] For example, a
 227 relationship of $\mu \propto T^{-1.5}$ indicates that, rather than impurity scattering, the electron transport is
 228 governed by acoustic phonon scattering.^[50] To evaluate the charge-carrier mobility dynamics, we
 229 measured temperature-dependent SCLC (from 88 K to 303 K) in the vertical device structure. By

230 fitting the curves where the current is limited by space charge (Fig. S8), we extracted the mobility
 231 as a function of temperature. As shown in Fig. S9, the mobility decreases with increasing
 232 temperature in all cases. The dashed red line (Fig. S9) represents the fitted mobility-temperature
 233 relationship. The values of charge transport-phonon scattering relation (m) were estimated to be -
 234 1.45, -1.58, -1.32, and -1.02 for PMA₂PbCl₄, PEA₂PbCl₄, (PPA)₃Pb₂Cl₇, and (PBA)₃Pb₂Cl₇ (Table
 235 2), respectively. The temperature dependence of $T^{-1.45}$ and $T^{-1.58}$ observed for the PMA-based and
 236 PEA-based samples indicates their band-like transport which is rationalized by phonon scattering.
 237 The dependence of $\sim T^{-1.5}$ is indicative of low defect concentration for PMA-based and PEA-based
 238 samples, e.g., the intrinsic semiconducting behavior.^[51] The smaller value of m obtained for
 239 (PPA)₃Pb₂Cl₇, and (PBA)₃Pb₂Cl₇ (-1.32 and -1.02) suggests the dominant role of other scattering
 240 mechanisms such as impurity scattering. The mobility at room temperature (293 K) is determined
 241 to be 0.335, 3.48×10^{-2} , 4.89×10^{-3} , and 5.74×10^{-4} cm² V⁻¹ s⁻¹ for PMA, PEA, PPA, and PBA-
 242 based samples (Table 2), respectively. We ascribed this due to a small carrier migration barrier in
 243 PMA₂PbCl₄, while the trap-assisted and interface recombination may affect charge mobility
 244 severely in the other three samples ^[34].

245 **Table 2.** The extracted values for the parameters of m and mobility at room temperature

Samples	m	mobility /cm ² V ⁻¹ s ⁻¹
PMA ₂ PbCl ₄	-1.45	0.335
PEA ₂ PbCl ₄	-1.58	3.48×10^{-2}
(PPA) ₃ Pb ₂ Cl ₇	-1.32	4.89×10^{-3}
(PBA) ₃ Pb ₂ Cl ₇	-1.02	5.74×10^{-4}

246 *Measured at 293 K)

247 We ascribed the charge transport in the QWs with the charge tunneling in the finite potential
 248 well model ^[52], where both the barrier length and barrier potential are considered. In this model,
 249 the tunneling transition rate of charge hopping across a barrier is described by tunneling decay
 250 constant (β), which we derived by fitting the plots of carrier mobility (μ) as a function of barrier
 251 length in terms of Miller-Abrahams expression.^[55] Figure S10 shows carrier mobility (μ) versus
 252 the barrier length (thickness estimated from the structural optimization) on a logarithmic scale for
 253 all the fabricated perovskites. The β value is noted to be 0.92 via fitting the plots, suggesting the

254 tunneling effect trend. The QWs structure with a smaller barrier length resulted in improved carrier
255 extraction with high mobility. Arguably, it is rational to decipher that the carrier mobility in 2D
256 PMA, PEA-based films is comparable to that of 3D counterparts.^[1]

257 We further corroborated our findings with density functional theory (DFT) calculations on
258 carrier confinement. Figure S11 illustrates the band structure of PMA-, PEA-, PPA-, and PBA-
259 based perovskites, respectively. Owing to the 2D and 1D electronic dimensionality, both the
260 conduction band minimum (CBM) and valence band maximum (VBM) are dispersive along
261 inorganic octahedrons, leading to a limited charge carrier in the transport direction. For all four
262 perovskites, highly dispersive conduction features and valence band edges within the PbCl_4^{2-} and
263 $\text{Pb}_2\text{Cl}_7^{3-}$ direction and the flat band edges along the organic layer were exhibited in the plots for
264 band edges. We noted that the perovskites with 2D structure ($\text{PMA}_2\text{PbCl}_4$, $\text{PEA}_2\text{PbCl}_4$) manifest
265 high dispersion while 1D structure ($(\text{PPA})_3\text{Pb}_2\text{Cl}_7$ and $(\text{PBA})_3\text{Pb}_2\text{Cl}_7$) appears an inconspicuous
266 dispersive profile. All the perovskites exhibit a direct band gap at the Γ point behavior, which is
267 necessary for semiconductors applied in the photodetector.

268 We deduced a band lineup between the inorganic and organic layers in the density of states
269 (DOS) plots (Fig. S12).^[56] Figure 3a,b presents the deduced type-I band alignment of 2D
270 ($\text{PMA})_2\text{PbCl}_4$ and ($\text{PEA})_2\text{PbCl}_4$ compounds by considering the DFT band gap.^[57] Here, for the
271 ($\text{PMA})_2\text{PbCl}_4$ (Figure 3a), the corresponding band alignments show the relevant confinement
272 potential of 0.47 eV for the electron confinement potential (V_e) and 0.53 eV for hole confinement
273 potentials (V_h). As for the ($\text{PEA})_2\text{PbCl}_4$ (Figure 3b), the V_e appears a larger value (0.71 eV) while
274 the V_h has a similar value (0.51 eV). The increase of V_e in ($\text{PEA})_2\text{PbCl}_4$ reveals the pronounced
275 type-I carrier confinement. The organic layer with a narrow bandgap in ($\text{PPA})_3\text{Pb}_2\text{Cl}_7$ and
276 ($\text{PBA})_3\text{Pb}_2\text{Cl}_7$ results in a type-II bandgap alignment, in which the inorganic layer and organic
277 layer acts as “well” and “barrier”, respectively. However, such arrangement also contributes to a
278 relatively poor carrier extraction performance, typically as a shortcoming of 1D electronic
279 structure. Thus, the 2D perovskite films with homogeneous energy landscapes are the key to
280 addressing the electrical modulation. Figure 3c compares the deduced confinement potentials (V_e ,
281 V_h , and V_e/V_h) for all the perovskite samples, in which the barrier length increases from PMA
282 (14.21 Å) to PEA (15.50 Å), PPA (16.76 Å), and PBA (17.14 Å), respectively. Both for 2D and

283 1D perovskite structures, a small V_e results in a weak confinement effect for easy carrier extraction,
 284 thus inducing improvement in electrical properties.

285 The coulombic interaction between organic cations and PbCl_4^{2-} octahedra impact significantly
 286 on the electronic structure of hybrid materials. To elucidate the intrinsic electron diffusion
 287 difference, electron potential profiles in 2D $(\text{PMA})_2\text{PbCl}_4$ and $(\text{PEA})_2\text{PbCl}_4$ thin films with similar
 288 building blocks were computed by DFT calculations (Figures 3, d, and e). The calculated electron
 289 diffusion barriers at different sites point to local minima in our perovskite structure at interstitial
 290 sites or within inorganic/organic layers. Compared with the $(\text{PEA})_2\text{PbCl}_4$, the $(\text{PMA})_2\text{PbCl}_4$ -based
 291 composites manifest a smaller maximum electron diffusion barrier (0.786 eV in $(\text{PMA})_2\text{PbCl}_4$ and
 292 1.007 eV in $(\text{PEA})_2\text{PbCl}_4$ from inorganic layer to organic layer). This reveals an impact of organic
 293 layer thickness on the coulombic interaction difference in 2D perovskite. Arguably, the small
 294 electron diffusion barrier in $(\text{PMA})_2\text{PbCl}_4$ film corresponds to large carrier mobility.

295
 296

297 **Fig. 3. Schematic diagram of four possible QW band structures from DFT calculation. (a,b)**

298 The computed band alignments and carriers confinement potentials for $(\text{PMA})_2\text{PbCl}_4$ and

299 (PEA)₂PbCl₄ were extracted from corresponding DOS plots (Fig. S12). (c) Variation of the hole
300 and electron confinement potentials and corresponding ratios extracted from Figure 3a,b and
301 Figure S13; (d,e) DFT-calculated potential profiles for the (PMA)₂PbCl₄ and (PEA)₂PbCl₄ based
302 perovskite lattice.

303
304 We fabricated (Figure 4a) the planar perovskite heterojunction UPD devices with an architect
305 of glass/ITO/SnO₂/perovskite/PTAA:poly-TPD/Au to probe their photoelectrical parameters. To
306 examine the capability of the devices for self-powered photodetection, we carried out the optical
307 response characteristic measurements in self-powered mode. Table S2 lists the parameters in terms
308 of photo-responsivity, response time, noise property, and specific detectivity of UPDs based on
309 four low-dimensional perovskites. The photocurrent density was measured with a 325 nm LED
310 incident from the glass side with a power density of 2.54 mW cm⁻². Figure 4b illustrates the time-
311 dependent transient photocurrent ($J_{ph}-t$) under one on/off switching cycle. Particularly, the devices
312 based on 2D PMA- and PEA-perovskites exhibited considerably higher photocurrent values of
313 0.48 mA cm⁻² and 0.34 mA cm⁻², respectively. By contrast, the 1D-PPA₃Pb₂Cl₇ and (PBA)₃Pb₂Cl₇
314 devices showed lower optical response performance (0.07 mA cm⁻² and 0.04 mA cm⁻²). This trend
315 in photocurrent for different photo-sensitive layers was repetitive (Fig. S14). A transient current
316 peak is observed in PPA- and PBA-based devices after the light source turn-on. This phenomenon
317 may result from the trapping and de-trapping processes to equilibrate the trap population,
318 suggesting a large amount of trap density in 1D perovskites.^[58] Arguably, to acquire the signals
319 rapidly, the response speed is important for self-powered photodetector applications. We
320 characterized the response feature (rise time (t_{rise}) and fall time (t_{fall})) by illuminating them with a
321 rectangular light pulse at 5 kHz. As shown (Figure S15), the 2D-PMA₂PbCl₄ exhibited the highest
322 response speed with t_{rise} and t_{fall} of 12.1 μs and 14.6 μs, respectively. Such a response time is four
323 times shorter than the lowest value in 1D-PPA₃Pb₂Cl₇ devices (t_{rise} , 56.3 μs and t_{fall} , 60.1 μs),
324 suggesting the superior charge transport properties in 2D-PMA₂PbCl₄. These values are obtained
325 by an average of 30 separate devices.

326 For photodetector applications, it is critical to calibrate the magnitude of the photocurrent
327 corresponding to per unit power described as Responsivity (R, $R=J_{ph}(\lambda)/P_{opt}(\lambda)$). The responsivity
328 (*i.e.*, sensitivity) of UPDs at various incident optical power densities were measured and plotted

329 (Fig. S16). The largest R-value of 0.247 A W^{-1} is from $\text{PMA}_2\text{PbCl}_4$ -based device. The small value
 330 of responsivity from devices with 1D structured perovskite could correspond to the low
 331 photocurrent. We evaluated the dependence of the photocurrent on the incident optical power
 332 density (Figure 4c) with the power law of $J_{ph} \propto P_{opt}^\theta$ to gain further insight into the photo-
 333 conversion process. The self-powered photodetectors were illuminated by $\lambda = 325 \text{ nm}$ with variable
 334 optical power densities from $0.07 \mu\text{W cm}^{-2}$ to 8.44 mW cm^{-2} . The 2D- $\text{PMA}_2\text{PbCl}_4$ and $\text{PEA}_2\text{PbCl}_4$
 335 delivered a photocurrent density proportional to the incident optical power while the 1D
 336 perovskite-based device manifested low linearity. For realistic applications, photodetectors are
 337 required to deliver a linear photo-response to optical power. The linear relationship can be
 338 expressed by the exponent θ , amounting to 0.98 ($(\text{PMA})_2\text{PbCl}_4$), 0.97 ($(\text{PEA})_2\text{PbCl}_4$), 0.83
 339 ($(\text{PPA})_3\text{Pb}_2\text{Cl}_7$) and 0.69 ($(\text{PBA})_3\text{Pb}_2\text{Cl}_7$) for all the four perovskites, respectively. The deduced
 340 sublinear response in the performance of 1D- $\text{PPA}_3\text{Pb}_2\text{Cl}_7$ and $(\text{PBA})_3\text{Pb}_2\text{Cl}_7$ entails ineffective
 341 carrier utilization. Aiding from the excellent carrier extraction properties, the PMA- and PEA-
 342 based device imply a weak signal detectivity with a low detective limit of $0.07 \mu\text{W cm}^{-2}$.

343
 344 **Fig. 4. The UPD devices characterization.** (a) Schematic of the photodetectors structure; (b) The
 345 photocurrent density of $(\text{PMA})_2\text{PbCl}_4$, $(\text{PEA})_2\text{PbCl}_4$, $(\text{PPA})_3\text{Pb}_2\text{Cl}_7$, and $(\text{PBA})_3\text{Pb}_2\text{Cl}_7$ -based
 346 devices measured with 325 nm LED with a power density of 2.54 mW cm^{-2} . (c) The corresponding
 347 photocurrent density (J_{ph}) of the UPDs measured at 0 V as a function of the incident optical power
 348 density (P_{opt}). (d) The current noise power spectrum of the photodetector measured at 0 V. (e) The

349 working stability of a device under continuous light irradiation at 325 nm over 14000 s; and (f) the
350 long-term stability of un-encapsulated photodetectors under ambient conditions with RH of 25%
351 and temperature of 25 °C, the error bar was from 5 devices.

352 Figure 4d presents the devices' noise current from which the lowest noise of $0.35 \text{ pA Hz}^{-1/2}$ at
353 1 Hz can be observed for the 2D-PMA₂PbCl₄ device, and the white noise instead of the 1/f noise
354 dominates at high frequency (>1 kHz). The general low noise current of four devices is
355 characteristic of the confined charge transport within the quantum plane in low-dimensional
356 perovskite films. Then, the noise equivalent power (NEP) was calculated according to: $\text{NEP} = i_n/R$,
357 where i_n is the measured noise current. A low value of NEP of 1.43 and 2.71 $\text{pW Hz}^{-1/2}$ for the
358 UPDs based on 2D-PMA₂PbCl₄ and PEA₂PbCl₄ is noted. Based on the excellent device
359 performance with 2D-perovskite, the specific detectivity (D^*) can further be obtained by the
360 equation of $D^* = (A \times f_{-3\text{dB}})^{1/2} / \text{NEP}$, where A is the active area and $f_{-3\text{dB}}$ is the bandwidth extracted
361 from Figure S17. A higher value of D^* (6.32×10^{13} jones) for the PMA₂PbCl₄ device represents a
362 remarkable photoelectric performance benefit from the improved photo-excited carrier extraction
363 efficiency.

364 To access the reliability, we undertook the stability measurements of the (PMA)₂PbCl₄-based
365 photodetectors without encapsulation by tracking their responsivity continuously with exposure to
366 325 nm (2.54 mW cm^{-2}) over 14000 s (Figure 4e). The noted continuous stability is significantly
367 higher than previous reports based on their 3D perovskites.^[1] Specifically, the unencapsulated
368 devices manifested considerably higher stability over 60 days of storage in ambient air (relative
369 humidity (RH): 25%, temperature: 25 °C) (Figure 4f). We further demonstrated the UV imaging
370 capability of (PMA)₂PbCl₄-based UPDs by constructing an imaging protocol. When the sample
371 characters 'HUST' as imaging objects were exposed to a 325 nm light source (Fig. S18a)
372 accompanied by white illumination, a clear image was obtained by tracking the UPDs output signal
373 current (Fig. S18b). A sharp contrast can be noted on the resultant current image, indicating that
374 the photodetectors manifest potential for fast and accurate imaging in the UV region with low
375 background interference.

376

377

378 Discussion

379 The high selectivity and responsivity in low dimensional perovskite-based UV photodetector
380 are attributed to the optimization of a carrier transmission path. The 2D perovskite with a thinner
381 organic layer manifests high conductivity anisotropy with $\sigma_{\text{out-plane}}$ much larger than $\sigma_{\text{in-plane}}$, which
382 is conducive to the longitudinal extraction of carriers (Fig. S3). The restriction of carrier motion
383 along the in-plane direction in our semiconductors is attributed to the presence of organic layers
384 that can efficiently suppress the noise current (0.35, 0.41, 0.43, and 0.46 pA Hz^{-1/2} for
385 (PMA)₂PbCl₄, (PEA)₂PbCl₄, (PPA)₃Pb₂Cl₇, and (PBA)₃Pb₂Cl₇-based devices). The current state-
386 of-the-art indicates most of the responsivity of low dimensional perovskite-based devices is
387 typically much smaller than that of 3D counterparts as the large resistance makes it more difficult
388 for carrier extraction. Here, we demonstrated a melioration of responsivity in 2D PMA-perovskite-
389 based UPDs *via* inhibition of electron-phonon scattering and exciton binding energy. Mechanistic
390 inside reveals that the exciton binding energy in low-dimensional lead chlorine hybrid perovskites
391 is tens of meV (Table 1, only 62.91 meV for (PMA)₂PbCl₄), and thus excitons can be ionized by
392 thermal excitation easily. Such ionized excitons are essential to promoting the photocurrent and
393 thus the responsivity. Furthermore, the QWs with small carrier transport barrier potential formed
394 in the (PMA)₂PbCl₄ perovskite films computed with DFT calculations support the inherent
395 electrical merits (Figure 3). Thus, the photo-responsivity has been achieved in vertical devices
396 (Figure 4a) at 0 V bias featuring a unique low noise current for low dimensional perovskite-based
397 devices with a high D^* characteristic (Table S2). Notably, the 2D perovskite-based UPDs inherit
398 high environmental stability.

399 To conclude, we showed the key impact of quantum confinement in layered perovskite on their
400 photoelectric conversion capacities for developing easy-to-fabricate UV photodetectors. The thin-
401 film merits of solution-processed photoactive layers of PMA₂PbCl₄, PEA₂PbCl₄, PPA₃Pb₂Cl₇, and
402 (PBA)₃Pb₂Cl₇ probed with an array of techniques. When compared to the other three analogs, the
403 ultraviolet photodetectors based on PMA₂PbCl₄ absorbers gave significantly superior self-
404 powered photodetector performance. Our work offers a material design rule for the exploration of
405 a high-performance self-powered photodetector by uncovering the mechanistic modulation of
406 band structure alignment to lower exciton-binding energy and thus improve carrier mobility.

407 **Methods**

408 **Materials and Reagents.** Poly-TPD and PTAA were purchased from Xi'an p-OLED. PbCl₂
409 (99.99%) was purchased from Sigma-Aldrich. Benzylamine (PMA), β-phenylethylamine (PEA),
410 3-phenyl-1-propylamine (PPA), 4-phenyl-1-butylamine (PBA) were purchased from Macklin. The
411 synthesis details of the four phenyl alkylammonium hydrochloride were described in the
412 supporting information.

413 **Supplementary Materials**

414 Experimental details for thin-film preparation for UV photodetector fabrication, and
415 characterizations and measurements. are described in Supporting Information.

416

417 **References**

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- 570

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582

583 **Author contributions:**

584 M.W. directed the research project and supervised the experimental design. Z.L. conceived the
585 idea and performed most of the experiments. H.Y. and X.L. assisted in device fabrication and film
586 measurements. Z.Z. and F.W. contributed to the first-principles calculation. Z.Z. and W.L. assisted
587 in femtosecond transient absorption measurements. Q.S assisted in analyzing the data. Z.L., S.A.
588 and M.W. wrote the paper. All authors discussed the results and commented on the manuscript.

589

590 **Competing interests:** The authors declare no competing financial interest. The authors declare no
591 competing interests. A chinse patent authored by Z.L. and M.W is pending.

592

593 **Data and materials availability:**

594 Data and materials are available if required.